

TOTAL FATIGUE LIFE MODEL FOR T700 CARBON/VINYL ESTER COMPOSITES- MODE I LOADING

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SUMMARY: Total fatigue life methodology proposed previously was applied to T700 carbon/vinyl ester composite laminate for marine applications. T700 carbon fiber has high fracture strain and strength and intermediate modulus. Multilayer and multiaxial fibers knitted by polyester fibers are available as stitch bonded fabric. Mode-I fracture test was conducted to obtain the fracture resistance G_{IR} as a function of delamination extension. Fatigue onset life test was conducted to determine the threshold energy release rate, G_{Ith} . The fracture resistance equation was $G_{IR}=0.175+0.56(a-a_0)^{0.39}$ and $G_{Ith}=0.18G_{IC}$, where $G_{IC}=0.175\text{kJ/mm}^2$. Constant amplitude cyclic opening displacement fatigue test was conducted to establish the delamination growth rate da/dN as a function of maximum cyclic energy release rate G_{Imax}/G_{IR} . The total life equation was found to be

$$\frac{da}{dN} = 0.076 \left(\frac{G_{Imax}}{G_{IR}} \right)^{6.57} \left(1 - \left(\frac{G_{Ith}}{G_{Imax}} \right)^8 \right) / \left(1 - \left(\frac{G_{Imax}}{G_{IR}} \right)^2 \right). \text{ The equation fits the test data very}$$

well in subcritical and linear domains.

KEYWORDS: Fatigue, Delamination growth rate, Resistance curve, T700 carbon/vinyl ester, Threshold

INTRODUCTION

Susceptibility to delamination is a major weakness of composite laminates. Knowledge of material's resistance to interlaminar fracture and fatigue is essential to establish design allowable and damage tolerance guidelines for structures. Fracture mechanics based delamination growth models are required to predict fatigue life and establish suitable inspection intervals so that a delamination can be found and repaired long before it becomes critical or exceeds the residual strength of the component. Fatigue delamination growth laws that cover the threshold, the stable growth and the unstable fracture domains are needed for total life estimation. Such growth laws were proposed in the past for metallic materials^[1,2] and are now becoming accepted in damage tolerant designs. In this methodology, the delamination growth rate consists of three domains, namely subcritical (slow), linear, and unstable growth rate domains. The growth rate depends on microscope details of material in domain 1; on crack driving force in domain 2; and on the fracture characteristics in the unstable domain 3.

In composite laminates substantial research^[3-15] has been done on delamination growth laws in domain 2. The data has been expressed by power law equation in G_{Imax} or ΔG_{Imax} by curve

fits. Research efforts also focused on the effect of stress ratio^[3, 4], matrix toughness^[5, 6], and pure and mixed mode stress states^[4, 6, 7]. Poursartip^[14] first introduced the importance of resistance curve and proposed G_R normalization da/dN equation for edge delaminated composite specimens. Recently, Paris and O'Brien^[15] and Shivakumar et al^[16, 17] proposed an approach for total da/dN equation that included the resistance effect as shown in Fig. 1. Reference 16 and 17 also presents a step by step approach of testing and data reduction to develop the total life for FGI 1854 woven-roving glass fiber/vinyl ester composite laminate subjected to mode I loading. The equation was verified by experiments for cyclic block loading.

The present study extends the methodology to the T700 carbon/vinyl ester composite for marine application. The materials selected are Toray T700 carbon fiber and Dow's Derakane 510A-40 vinyl ester. The T700 carbon fiber has relatively low cost and high strength and is of particular interest to the Navy for marine application. In this paper, the fracture resistance (G_{IR}) result obtained from the fracture test, fatigue threshold energy release rate (G_{Ith}) obtained from the fatigue onset test and the fatigue growth results determined by the fatigue growth test are presented. Finally a total fatigue life model normalized by fracture resistance G_{IR} under mode I loading is established.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology and test procedures for developing total fatigue life are similar to those described in Ref. 16 and 17 and are briefly explained below.

Assumptions

1. Interlaminar fracture resistance (G_{IR}) increases with delamination length (a). The resistance curve $G_{IR}(a)$ can be expressed as a function of initiation fracture toughness G_{IC} and the delamination extension ($a-a_0$). The initial delamination length is a_0 .
2. The da/dN is proportional to the driving force G_{Imax} and inversely proportional to the delamination resistance G_{IR} at the current delamination location.
3. The da/dN is bounded by two extreme values of G_{Imax} ; the threshold energy release rate G_{Ith} at or below which da/dN is nearly zero (no growth) and the G_{IR} at which da/dN is very large or unstable (infinite). Note that G_{IR} is a function of delamination growth.
4. The value of G_{Ith} can be determined by fatigue delamination onset test as per ASTM D6115.

Approach

As in metallic material, da/dN data for composite laminates also falls into three domains, namely, subcritical or slow crack growth domain, G_{Imax} controlled domain (or Paris' domain), and the unstable or fracture domain (see a typical Fig.1). From the assumptions 1 and 2, the da/dN in domain 2 is written in a power law form as:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A \left[\frac{G_{Imax}(a)}{G_{IR}(a)} \right]^m \quad (1)$$

where A and m are material constants to be determined from the curve fit to the test data.

In the subcritical domain, the da/dN (assumption 3) varies between zero (when $G_{Imax} \leq G_{Ith}$) and a value that matches domain 2. The form of the da/dN equation can be written as:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A \left(\frac{G_{I_{max}}}{G_{IR}} \right)^m \left[1 - \left(G_{I_{th}} / G_{I_{max}} \right)^{D_1} \right] \quad (2)$$

The exponent D_1 is determined from curve fit to the test data.

In the unstable domain, da/dN varies between ∞ (when $G_{I_{max}}=G_{IR}$) and the transition value that matches Eqn. 1 in domain 2. The form of the da/dN equation can be written as:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A \left(\frac{G_{I_{max}}}{G_{IR}} \right)^m \frac{1}{\left[1 - \left(G_{I_{max}} / G_{IR} \right)^{D_2} \right]} \quad (3)$$

The exponent D_2 is a material parameter determined from the curve fit to the test data.

Finally, the combined da/dN equation that covers all three domains is:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A \left(\frac{G_{I_{max}}}{G_{IR}} \right)^m \frac{\left(1 - \left(\frac{G_{I_{th}}}{G_{I_{max}}} \right)^{D_1} \right)}{\left(1 - \left(\frac{G_{I_{max}}}{G_{IR}} \right)^{D_2} \right)} \quad (4)$$

The values of A , m , D_1 and D_2 are the material parameters to be determined by curve fit to the fatigue test data.

Test Procedure for Establishing the Parameters

- a. Conduct mode-I fracture test using the DCB specimen and establish resistance curve $G_{IR}(a)$ as per ASTM D5528^[18]. Fit a G_{IR} versus a equation. Many times a power law equation fits the data very well.
- b. Conduct ASTM D-6115^[19] fatigue onset life test and establish the $G_{I_{th}}$ by a curve fit and a chosen onset life criteria.
- c. Conduct a fatigue test on a virgin DCB specimen with $G_{I_{max}}$ value about 0.3 G_{IC} till the compliance change is about 2% for unidirectional and 5% for textile preform composites. This ensures a natural delamination to initiate yet the resistance change from G_{IC} is very small and $G_{IR}=G_{IC}$ can be assumed.
- d. Conduct a constant amplitude displacement controlled fatigue test starting with a $G_{I_{max}}$ value that is slightly lower than G_{IC} . A good starting value is about $G_{I_{max}}=0.8G_{IC}$. Continue the test till the delamination growth rate becomes very small (for example, $da/dN \leq 10^{-7}$ in/cycle).
- e. Repeat the test at least for three specimens and plot the data as da/dN versus $(G_{I_{max}}/G_{IR})$ on a \log - \log graph.
- f. Divide the plot into three domains by visual inspection (see Fig. 1). The middle linear region and the two ends, namely subcritical and unstable regions.
- g. Perform least square \log - \log fit to the domain 2 data and determine the constants A and m .
- h. Determine D_1 of Eqn. 2, using already determined A and m by fitting the equation to domains 1 and 2 data. A trial and error approach works well.
- i. Finally determine D_2 of Eqn. 3 by fitting the equation to domains 2 and 3 data as in step 'h'.
- j. Using the constants determined above plot Eqn. 4 and compare it with the test data. If the fit is not satisfactory repeat steps 'f' through 'j'.

MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The carbon stitch bonded fabric designated by LT650-C12 was supplied by Devold AMT AS, Sweden. This was a equi-biaxial fabric produced using Toray's Torayca T700 24k carbon fiber tow with a vinyl ester compatible sizing (FOE). The aerial weight of the fabric was 634 gm/sqm with 315 gm/sqm in the 0° direction and 305 gm/sqm in the 90° direction tied together with 14 gm/sqm polyester knitting thread. Toray's Torayca T700 carbon fiber was chosen because of its relatively low cost and high strength. The T700 fiber had a tensile strength of 4.9 GPa, a tensile modulus of 230 GPa and an elongation of 2.1%.

The matrix used was Dow Chemical's Derakane 510A-40. It is a brominated vinyl ester formulated for the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. The bromination imparts a fire resistant property to the composite. The vinyl ester had a viscosity of 350 cps, which is ideal for the VARTM process. It can be catalyzed to give a wide range of pot life and cure time.

Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens were used in fracture test, fatigue onset test and fatigue growth test. An 8-ply composite panel was fabricated by VARTM process. The panel was postcured at 180 °F for 8 hours. After post curing, the panel was cut into 23 cm(L)x25mm(b)x5.6mm(h) specimens. The initial crack length is 38mm. The details of the VARTM process and specimen preparation are explained in Ref. 20. Figure 2 shows the DCB specimen configuration.

TESTING

All tests were carried out in a MTS test machine using a 890 N(200-lb) load cell. The test set up is the same for all three (fracture, fatigue onset and fatigue growth) tests. The piano hinge tabs of the specimen were mounted in the hydraulic grips of the load frame. A magnifying camera was mounted on a traversing stand (both vertical and horizontal) with vernier scale. The camera was connected to a TV monitor to locate and track the delamination tip. Figure 3 shows the test set up.

Fracture test

The mode-I fracture test using the DCB specimen was conducted as per ASTM D5528 and a resistance curve $G_{IR}(a)$ was established. At the start of each test the delamination-tip location was noted. The cross-head displacement was started and the delamination-tip propagation was monitored through the camera. The tests were conducted by displacement control loading with a cross-head rate of 0.5 mm/min. Load and cross-head displacements were recorded continuously throughout the test. The load-displacement data was recorded when the visual onset of delamination movement was observed on the edge of the specimen. The initial loading was stopped after an increment of delamination growth of about 5 mm. The specimen was unloaded at a constant cross-head rate of up to 25 mm/min. After unloading, the delamination tip position was marked on both edges of the specimen. If the difference of delamination length on the two edges is more than 2 mm, the test is invalid. The specimen was reloaded at the same constant cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min without stopping or unloading until the final delamination length increment is reached. The load and displacement values were recorded at every 1 mm increment in the first 5 mm delamination growth. Then they were recorded at every 5 mm growth until the delamination has propagated at least 45 mm and again at every 1 mm increment for the last 5 mm of delamination propagation.

The energy release rate G_I was calculated from the modified beam theory equation^[18]:

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (5)$$

where P = load, δ = load point displacement, b = specimen width, and a = delamination length. The parameter Δ is a crack length correction parameter for not perfectly built-in condition of the DCB. The Δ was determined from the specimen compliance and delamination length data^[18]. Energy release rate G_{IR} was plotted against delamination propagation $da = (a - a_0)$ as shown in Fig. 4. It shows an increased G_{IR} with delamination growth. A power law equation was fitted to the data and the resulting resistance equation is:

$$G_{IR} = 0.175 + 0.03(a - a_0)^{0.39} \quad (6)$$

The initial fracture toughness G_{IC} was determined by the 5% offset/maximum load (5%/Max)^[18]. The G_{IC} of this material is 0.175 kJ/m².

Fatigue onset test

The fatigue delamination growth onset life test was conducted as per ASTM D6115^[19] to obtain the threshold energy release rate G_{Ith} . All fatigue tests were conducted using specimens made from the same panel (batch) used for the fracture test. An expression relating the load-point displacement $\delta_{I_{max}}$ to $G_{I_{max}}$ at the onset of fracture (or at the visible delamination propagation) was determined. For a chosen value of maximum cyclic energy release rate ratio $f = G_{I_{max}}/G_{IC}$, $\delta_{I_{max}}$ was determined from the equation:

$$\delta_{I_{max}} = \sqrt{\frac{G_{I_{max}}}{G_{IC}} \left(\frac{a_0 + \Delta}{a_{IC} + \Delta} \right)^2} \delta_{IC} \quad (7)$$

where a_0 is the initial crack length for this fatigue onset life test, a_{IC} is the initial crack length for the fracture test, Δ is the crack length correction parameter obtained from the fracture test, and δ_{IC} is the load-point displacement when the crack starts to grow for the virgin specimen.

The cyclic loading ratio (R) selected was 0.1, from this value $\delta_{I_{min}}$ was determined ($\delta_{I_{min}} = R\delta_{I_{max}}$). Values of $\delta_{I_{max}}$ for ($G_{I_{max}}/G_{IC}$) of 0.5, 0.3, 0.25, 0.2 and 0.15 were calculated and used for testing. Each $\delta_{I_{max}}$ was tested for three specimens.

The test machine was set to the stroke loading at a frequency of 1 Hz between $\delta_{I_{max}}$ and 0.1 $\delta_{I_{max}}$. At first, the specimen was displaced to $\delta_{I_{max}}$ and the maximum load $P_{I_{max}}$ was recorded. From $\delta_{I_{max}}$ and $P_{I_{max}}$ values the initial compliance at $N=1$ was determined and the actual $G_{I_{max}}$ were calculated using:

$$G_{I_{max}} = \frac{3P_{I_{max}}\delta_{I_{max}}}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (8)$$

The machine displacement was slowly reduced to zero and the fatigue test was started. The load and displacement were recorded at every cycle using a Vishey 5000 data acquisition system. The test was continued for predetermined 50k cycles for higher values of $G_{I_{max}}/G_{IC}$ and up to 200k cycles for $G_{I_{max}}/G_{IC}=0.15$.

The ASTM standard D-6115^[19] recommended two criteria to determine the number of cycles N for the onset of delamination growth, namely 1% and 5% increase of the compliance compared to the compliance at $N=1$. In this research, 1% and 2% increases in compliance were examined to establish the onset life. Figure 5 shows a plot of $G_{I_{max}}$ versus $\log N$ data for 1% and 2% criteria. O'Brien^[7] suggested that the correlation of $G_{I_{max}}$ and $\log N$ at $10^0 \leq N \leq 10^6$ can be expressed by a linear equation and the G_{Ith} can be determined from that equation when

$N=10^6$. For the present material, the power law equation fits the $G_{I_{max}}$ versus $\log N$ data better than the linear equation. Therefore a power law equation fit was performed to determine the $G_{I_{th}}$. The equation is $G_{I_{max}}=0.25(\log N+1.38)^{-1.02}$. The equation agrees very well with the 1% and 2% compliance change criteria (see Fig. 5). The threshold energy release rate ($G_{I_{th}}$) was calculated from the equation when $N=10^6$ cycles and was found to be $0.18G_{IC}$. This $G_{I_{th}}$ was used to develop constants in delamination growth rate equation.

Fatigue growth test

The fatigue delamination growth test was similar to the onset life test. The test was conducted under constant amplitude cyclic displacement loading at the frequency range of 1-4 Hz with an R ratio of 0.1.

All test specimens were precracked by conducting fatigue tests at the load equivalent to $G_{I_{max}}=0.3G_{IC}$ till the specimens had compliance changes by 5%. Then new delamination lengths were measured and recorded. Delamination growth rate data was generated by the compliance method. The fatigue test was started at $\delta_{I_{max}}$ equivalent to $G_{I_{max}}/G_{IC}=0.8$ and run continuously. $\delta_{I_{max}}$ was calculated by Eqn. 7. During the test, the load ($P_{I_{max}}$) and the number of cycles (N) were continuously recorded. The compliance C which equals to $\delta_{I_{max}}/P_{I_{max}}$ was generated for all corresponding values of N . The compliance was plotted versus the number of cycles N . The delamination length a corresponding to the compliance value can be determined from the compliance-delamination length relationship found in the previous fracture test. From these results, da/dN was established. G_{IR} and $G_{I_{max}}$ were calculated by using Equations 6 and 8, respectively. Figure 6 shows the plot of da/dN versus $G_{I_{max}}/G_{IR}$ data for three different specimens. The G_{IR} was calculated from the fracture resistance equation at the current delamination length.

TOTAL FATIGUE LIFE EQUATION

In Fig. 6, the test data are bounded by the limits $G_{I_{max}}=G_{I_{th}}$ and $G_{I_{max}}/G_{IR}=1$. The $G_{I_{th}}$ from the onset life test was $0.18 G_{IC}$ and the upper limit $G_{I_{max}}/G_{IR}=1$ is from the condition that when $G_{I_{max}}=G_{IR}$ the delamination growth rate is infinite or unstable. However, almost all fatigue growth rate data fall in subcritical (slow growth) and linear domain. There are not enough data in unstable growth domain. The possible reason is that all three fatigue growth tests were started at $\delta_{I_{max}}$ equivalent to $G_{I_{max}}/G_{IC}=0.8$. Since fracture resistance G_{IR} increases instantaneously from G_{IC} to almost $1.5G_{IC}$ (Fig. 4), under the tested $\delta_{I_{max}}$ most $G_{I_{max}}/G_{IR}$ values remain below 0.7. This suggests that more test data with higher $\delta_{I_{max}}$ are needed to characterize the total life.

A least square $\log\text{-}\log$ equation fit was performed for the linear domain of $0.25 \leq G_{I_{max}}/G_{IR} \leq 0.7$. The constants A and m in Eqn. 1 were found to be 0.076 and 6.57, respectively. Subsequently, the exponent D_1 in Eqn. 2 was determined by trial and error approach to best fit the data in domains 1 and 2 and was found to be 8. Since there are not enough data in unstable fracture domain, the value of D_2 for glass/vinyl ester composite^[16, 17] was applied to hypothesize the exponent for this material. The final equation of da/dN that covers all three domains is:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = 0.076 \left(\frac{G_{Imax}}{G_{IR}} \right)^{6.57} \frac{\left(1 - \left(\frac{G_{Ith}}{G_{Imax}} \right)^8 \right)}{\left(1 - \left(\frac{G_{Imax}}{G_{IR}} \right)^2 \right)} \quad (9)$$

Figure 6 compares Eqn. 9 with the test data. The equation fits the test data very well in subcritical and linear domains. The total fatigue life methodology proposed previously was successfully applied to characterize the fatigue delamination property of T700 carbon/vinyl ester laminate.

CONCLUSIONS

Total fatigue life methodology proposed in previous study was applied to T700 carbon/vinyl ester composite laminate for marine applications. T700 carbon fiber has high fracture strain and strength and intermediate modulus. Multilayer and multiaxial fibers knitted by polyester fibers are available as stitch bonded fabric. Mode-I fracture test was conducted to obtain the fracture resistance G_{IR} as a function of delamination extension. Fatigue onset life test was conducted to determine the threshold energy release rate, G_{Ith} . The resistance equation was $G_{IR}=0.175+0.56(a-a_0)^{0.39}$ and $G_{Ith}=0.18G_{IC}$, where $G_{IC}=0.175\text{kJ/m}^2$. Constant amplitude cyclic opening displacement fatigue test was conducted to establish the delamination growth rate da/dN as a function of maximum cyclic energy release rate G_{Imax}/G_{IR} . The total life

equation was found to be $\frac{da}{dN} = 0.076 \left(\frac{G_{Imax}}{G_{IR}} \right)^{6.57} \frac{\left(1 - \left(\frac{G_{Ith}}{G_{Imax}} \right)^8 \right)}{\left(1 - \left(\frac{G_{Imax}}{G_{IR}} \right)^2 \right)}$. The equation fits the test data very well in subcritical and linear domains.

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Fig. 1: Hypothetical plot of da/dN vs G_{Imax}/G_{IR}

Fig. 2: Specimen configuration

Fig. 3: Test set up

Fig. 4: Fracture resistance versus delamination growth

Fig. 5: Variation of onset life with $G_{I_{max}}$

Fig. 6: Delamination growth rate versus $G_{I_{max}}/G_{IR}$ and total life equation